

Evaluating and Ranking Factors Promoting Green Consumer Behavior on C2C E-Commerce Websites Using the PARETO – FUZZY – AHP – TOPSIS Model

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Abstract

In the context of strong digital transformation, online shopping has become the preferred choice of many consumers. Peer-to-peer (C2C) e-commerce models are developing rapidly, creating a flexible and diverse trading environment with products and prices. However, the rich amount of information and large number of sellers on these platforms make the product selection process complicated, leading interested consumers to get lost in the shopping matrix. In order to help consumers shop smarter, the study proposes applying the integrated model set PARETO - FUZZY - AHP - TOPSIS to evaluate and rank factors affecting green consumer behavior in the context of online shopping on C2C websites.

Keywords: *E-commerce, green consumer behavior, C2C e-commerce model, Pareto principle, Fuzzy - AHP model, TOPSIS model, Fuzzy - AHP - TOPSIS model, C2C website ranking.*

JEL Classification codes: *E21, P64.*

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Introduction

The rapid development of e-commerce in the digital economy era has changed the way consumers approach and make shopping decisions. In particular, the green consumption trend is emerging as an important factor affecting online shopping behavior on C2C e-commerce platforms. However, the factors that shape green consumption behavior are often qualitative in nature, difficult to define clear boundaries, and are influenced by consumers' emotional perceptions. To overcome this limitation, the study proposes the use of the integrated model PARETO - FUZZY - AHP - TOPSIS as a multi-criteria approach, allowing for a more objective assessment of priority levels. Through this model, six typical C2C websites are evaluated and ranked according to the level of consumer choice in the context of green consumption. The research results are expected to provide empirical evidence to support the proposal of solutions to promote e-commerce development towards green consumption.

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Literature Review and Previous Research Studies

The Pareto principle, also known as the 80/20 rule, was proposed by Vilfredo Pareto (1897) after observing the distribution of wealth in society. Over time, this rule is not only limited to economics but has become an important tool in management analysis. In management science research, Pareto is used as an initial screening step that allows researchers to eliminate secondary factors to focus on the key group of factors that create the majority of the impact, thereby making the analysis more concise and accurate.

Fuzzy Logic was introduced by Zadeh (1965) as one of the important foundations of modern artificial intelligence science. Unlike traditional binary logic models (0-1), Fuzzy Logic describes intermediate states with true-false levels in a “fuzzy” form, reflecting more accurately how people think and evaluate in reality. In consumer behavior research, Fuzzy Logic helps quantify emotional assessments into fuzzy numbers, allowing for the handling of ambiguity in consumer choices, levels of agreement, or feelings. When combined with AHP, fuzzy-AHP increases reliability and reduces bias due to subjective feelings to create a solid foundation for the TOPSIS ranking step. AHP is a multi-criteria decision-making method developed by Professor Thomas L. Saaty in the 1970s. This method helps determine the priority of each factor influencing green purchasing decisions on C2C websites.

TOPSIS is a multi-criteria decision-making method proposed by Hwang and Yoon (1981), based on the principle: The optimal solution is the solution that has the closest distance to the positive ideal solution and the farthest distance to the negative ideal solution. In this study, it is used to rank the priority order for C2C websites.

Methodology and Proposed Model

The study was conducted over 5 months to survey 1,050 consumers and 8 experts from various positions in the field of e-commerce, including 4 lecturers who research and teach e-commerce, 1 e-commerce business operator, 1 digital marketing specialist, 1 marketing manager and 1 website programmer.

Step 1: Survey and collect data

Step 2: Apply Pareto to identify key factors.

Step 3: Identify a set of evaluation criteria based on core factors.

Step 4: Build a research model

Step 5: Create an evaluation matrix according to Fuzzy AHP

Step 6: Evaluate the impact of criteria on green consumer behavior

Step 7: Rank criteria that influence online shopping decisions

Step 8: Rank C2C websites in order of priority

Research model (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Hierarchical Structure Diagram
Source: Author's own proposed research model

Other domestic websites such as Tiki.vn (30.3%), Lazada.vn (18.7%), Chotot.com (12.4%), Sendo.vn (10.2%), and Taobao.vn (23.6%) are selected at an average level, reflecting the differentiation in consumer behavior depending on product type, pricing policy, and transaction experience. Although Tiki and Lazada previously operated under the B2C model, their expansion into the individual seller model has helped these two platforms to some extent participate in the C2C market. Meanwhile, Cho Tot and Sendo still maintain their role as old classifieds and sales platforms - suitable for the consumer group that prefers direct transactions and low prices.

In addition, the “Other” group (20%) includes emerging platforms such as Facebook Marketplace, Zalo, or small classifieds websites, demonstrating the flexible expansion of C2C consumer behavior to social media channels and mobile applications.

Based on the results of a survey of 1,050 consumers and interviews with 8 experts, 18 criteria were proposed to be included in the evaluation model. After using the Pareto 80/20 principle, 13 key factors were identified to be included in the evaluation model as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Table of Criteria Used in Evaluating C2C E-Commerce Websites

No.	Survey element	Proposed criteria in the model	Criteria code
1	Product brand	Green product brand	TC1
2	Selling price	Green selling price	TC2
3	Product quality	Green product quality	TC3
4	Product images	Green product images	TC4
5	Product information	Green product information	TC5
6	Online brand reputation	Green online brand reputation	TC6
7	Product catalog	Green product catalog	TC7
8	Shipping costs	Green shipping costs	TC8
9	Promotional program	Green Promotion Program	TC9
10	Payment method	Green payment method	TC10
11	Delivery time	Green delivery time	TC11
12	Return policy	Green return policy	TC12
13	Delivery unit	Green delivery unit	TC13

Source: Author's suggestion

The selected criteria for evaluation are the criteria that have a high level of influence on consumers' purchasing behavior when choosing to buy online on C2C websites.

Table 2. Table of Linguistic Variables and Corresponding Fuzzy Numbers

Language variables	Variable symbol	Language variable code	The corresponding triangular fuzzy numbers	Inverse of triangular fuzzy numbers
Equally important	BN	1	(1, 1, 3)	(1/3, 1/1, 1/1)
More importantly	TH	3	(1, 3, 5)	(1/5, 1/3, 1/1)
More important	NH	5	(3, 5, 7)	(1/7, 1/5, 1/3)
Very important	RT	7	(5, 7, 9)	(1/9, 1/7, 1/5)
Extremely important	CT	9	(7, 9, 9)	(1/9, 1/9, 1/7)

Source: Author's suggestion

In this study, this author will use the scale from 1 to 9 (Sodhi & Prabhakar, 2012) to convert the linguistic variable into Fuzzy number in Table 2. In which the selected conversions include 5 ranges to perform pairwise comparisons between fuzzy parameters. The linguistic variable will be converted to suit the survey and evaluation content. Typical websites used in the research model for evaluation are Shopee, Tiki, Lazada, Sendo, Chotot, Taobao will be denoted as W1, W2, W3, W4, W5, W6 respectively for convenience of calculation. The results of constructing the standardized matrix are as Table 3.

Table 3. Ranking of Influencing Factors According to the Standardized Matrix and Ideal Solution

Criteria	MT normalized weights						A ⁺	A ⁻	TC Ranking
	W1	W2	W3	W4	W5	W6			
TC1	0.194	0.228	0.143	0.139	0.143	0.186	0.228	0.139	6
TC2	0.157	0.183	0.132	0.151	0.170	0.151	0.132	0.183	12
TC3	0.205	0.149	0.136	0.149	0.111	0.136	0.205	0.111	4
TC4	0.206	0.225	0.159	0.168	0.178	0.234	0.234	0.159	8
TC5	0.217	0.235	0.181	0.163	0.163	0.254	0.254	0.163	7
TC6	0.213	0.190	0.167	0.144	0.190	0.213	0.213	0.144	9
TC7	0.269	0.192	0.154	0.154	0.173	0.250	0.269	0.154	5
TC8	0.200	0.154	0.154	0.162	0.177	0.177	0.154	0.200	11
TC9	0.214	0.182	0.190	0.127	0.111	0.174	0.214	0.111	3
TC10	0.200	0.166	0.146	0.133	0.113	0.139	0.200	0.113	2
TC11	0.216	0.216	0.164	0.138	0.138	0.198	0.138	0.216	13
TC12	0.233	0.183	0.166	0.133	0.124	0.183	0.233	0.124	1
TC13	0.188	0.204	0.157	0.141	0.141	0.173	0.204	0.141	10

Source: Author's suggestion

The most important criterion is the green return policy (TC12) with the highest CC value, the green return policy is identified as the factor that most strongly influences consumers' decision to choose a C2C platform. This shows that green shoppers are not only interested in the product itself but also pay attention to after-sales commitment, transparency and the "green" level of the return process.

The next group of criteria with the highest priority: Green payment method (TC10) ranked second, showing that consumers highly appreciate electronic payment methods to reduce paperwork and be environmentally friendly. Green promotion program (TC9) also has a significant influence, thereby reflecting the trend of consumers paying attention to incentives associated with environmental messages. Green product quality (TC3) continues to be a basic factor for consumers to evaluate the true value of environmentally friendly products. Green product categories (TC7)

are ranked in the important group, showing that the diversity of green products increases choice and promotes consumer purchasing behavior.

Medium-influence criteria group: Criteria such as green product brand (TC1), green product image (TC4), green product information (TC5), green online brand reputation (TC6) and green delivery unit (TC13) have a medium CC score, showing that consumers are still interested but do not consider this the most decisive factor.

Least-influence criteria group: Green selling price (TC2) is near the bottom, showing that consumers who buy green products do not consider price as the most important factor; they are willing to pay more for environmentally friendly products. Green shipping costs (TC8) have a low priority, possibly because platforms often have policies to support shipping costs or consumers consider this an additional cost, not a strong decision. Green delivery time (TC11) ranked last, showing that consumers are willing to accept slower delivery if it helps reduce carbon emissions or use environmentally friendly delivery methods.

The results emphasize that green consumer behavior on C2C platforms is not only dependent on the product itself but is also strongly influenced by: “Green” support service policies or transparency commitments and core quality of green products. In contrast, price and delivery speed are no longer the most important factors as in traditional shopping, showing that green consumers are willing to trade short-term benefits for more sustainable consumption.

Table 4. Table of Distance between Options and Closeness Index

Distance	Option options					
	W1	W2	W3	W4	W5	W6
d_i^+	0.012	0.023	0.049	0.068	0.073	0.041
d_i^-	0.067	0.039	0.018	0.010	0.009	0.041
$d_i^+ + d_i^-$	0,079	0.062	0.067	0.078	0.082	0.082
CCi	0.848	0.629	0.268	0.128	0.109	0.500
Ranking	1	2	4	5	6	3

Conclusion

Research results show that Shopee.vn is considered the most optimal C2C website for green online shopping behavior in Vietnam thanks to its ability to combine economic benefits and sustainable values, in line with modern consumer trends. Based on the research results, it is hoped that websites will be able to build their own competitive strategies in accordance with customer needs.

Proposing Optimal Solutions to Promote Green Consumer Behavior on C2C E-Commerce Websites

Green product quality: C2C needs to establish a seller verification system.

Green selling price: C2C needs to apply optimal selling price strategies.

Green product information: C2C needs to establish a dynamic information system for products.

Green product catalog: C2C needs to expand the green product catalog in 3 dimensions.

Green product image: C2C needs to build realistic illustrations.

Green product brand: C2C needs to strengthen public relations activities.

Green shipping cost: C2C needs to apply green cost and green delivery unit.

Green delivery time: C2C needs to establish a green scheduling system.

Green delivery unit: C2C needs to cooperate with units according to green standards.
Green return policy: C2C needs to establish a flexible return policy.
Green payment method: C2C needs to provide a variety of electronic payments.
Green promotion program: C2C needs to design in the direction of increasing social benefits.
Green website interface: C2C needs to design a friendly and easy-to-use interface.
Green online brand reputation: C2C needs to increase promotional activities through green brand ambassadors.

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